

AI Chatbots on Dating Sites Industry

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The Internet has introduced into society new paradigms related to practices that were previously introduced in the most diverse cultures of the world. The business relationship is marked by characteristics that correspond to the reality of each time but always related to the level of information.

Information is what drives business relationships. The product or service manufactured or provided by the supplier must reach the consumer's sphere of wealth, but for this to be implemented, the consumer needed to have prior knowledge of that object was being offered.

The established paradigm for the speed of information circulation in the virtual environment provides an overview of e-commerce development and future possibilities. In the same way, it weakens consumer protection, as it offers opportunities to implement businesses that lack the security that is achieved in a face-to-face relationship.

Thus, this swift panorama opens up the urgent need to establish instruments of protection and repression against illicit practices resulting from the virtual consumerist relationship, which begins with the legislative revision, through the adaptation of the justice system, and reaching the necessary education and preparation of the law.

E-commerce can be defined as digitally conducted business transactions (across the web or mobile devices) between organizations and between individuals - not necessarily an organization with an individual. These transactions are exchanges of money for products or services.

Business-to-Consumer is the most commonly known model and is characterized by selling a company to a customer. This sale may include products, travel, and other services, including online content. This can be divided into:

1. E-Tailer - Online Retail Store: Stores that are available to customers to shop digitally without having to leave home at any time. Some of these stores may have physical units as well or others may be the manufacturers themselves selling without intermediaries.
2. Community Provider: These are social networks where people with the same interests and hobbies can meet online.
3. Content Provider - Content Provider: Sites that provide content such as games, drawings, movies, newspapers, magazines, and music.

4. Portal - It is a more complete site, which tends to be the user's home page, where it usually offers news, searches, email, video streaming, chat, music such as Yahoo.

5. Transaction Brokers: These are online transaction facilitators or intermediaries designed to help clients do better and faster deals, such as stockbrokers and travel agents.

6. Market Creator - Marketplace: Companies that use it create a system that assists and connects sellers with buyers, such as eBay, Amazon or Free Market.

7. Service Provider - Service Providers: These are companies that offer services over the internet instead of products.

Social e-Commerce is commerce made through social networks, such as Facebook, Instagram, Pinterest, among others.

There is a certain convergence of Social eCommerce with Mobile e-commerce, as many of the social networks are accessed mainly via mobile phones. There is also a variation called conversational commerce, where the main conversation platforms are used as communication vehicles of companies with their customers, such as Whatsapp, Facebook Messenger, Snapchat, among others.

Despite being relatively new, the top 500 resellers of this model together gained \$ 3.9 billion in 2018. In addition to social networks, also in 2018, increased traffic on the websites of the top 500 sellers by 20%.

Social engineering is the strongest method of attacking the largest vulnerability of companies, their internal people. Cybercriminals recognize this fact. They know that the most vulnerable element of any information security system is the human being, who has behavioral and psychological traits that make him susceptible to attacks such as personal and/or professional vanity, self-confidence, willingness to be useful, willingness to make new friends.

Users Profiles

There are different ways in which someone uses a profile with false data. Some of the main ones are:

- a) Use of the false profile only to express anonymously, without harming others or committing unlawful acts;
- b) Use of profile to make a satire of known person;
- c) Use of false profiles to practice illegal acts.

It may happen that the perpetrator will act as if he or she is the victim and use his or her data in banking and other websites. This is what is known as identity theft.

If the fake profile is used to commit another offense, the perpetrator may be held liable for both crimes (ie in addition to false identity). Dual accountability will depend on the circumstances clarified in the police investigation, according to prosecution charges and court judgment. Some of the crimes that can be committed through false profiles willing to gain an illicit advantage over another person through fraudulent means.

Can social networking be held responsible?

In general, a company that maintains a social network on the Internet has no way of knowing that a certain user has entered false data in their registration. Therefore, it is generally understood that the social network is liable only if it is reported by the victim that there is a fake profile on his behalf and no action is taken to correct the problem.

Online dating social networks

Are sites that allow people to meet and introduce themselves to new people over the Internet to develop personal, romantic or sexual relationships.

These sites allow users to become members by simply creating a profile and submitting personal information such as age, gender, gender, location, photos etc.

They provide users with new and more popular ways to meet a new partner. Most fake profiles on dating sites are meant to create illegal connections like sex, etc. There are several fake bride and groom profiles on shadi.com that have set up their profiles with other names and are looking for ideal partners.

When someone shows interest in them, they start taking advantage by asking for their contact numbers and other personal information.

Usually, they deceive people and play with their emotions. One of the most dangerous people in dating OSNs is Catfishers - a person who uses online dating sites to entice people into a fraudulent romance.

Catfisher's main goal is financial gain by establishing an online relationship with other users and ultimately asking for money.

Catfish exploit fake profiles to entice weak women or men to fall in love and transfer money and other beneficial things to them. In addition to financial gain, other goals of these phantom profiles are to leverage online communications and manipulation.

The fake online dating profile issue is rising like a tsunami and it continues to sink all the real singles out there in the land of online dating.

It is estimated that out of 10 online dating profiles, at least five is considered fake, and per year more than \$ 50 million is lost in romance scams.

Fake online dating has opened the door for liars, thieves, cheats and the sex industry to take advantage of online dating sites.

Dating Chatbots are already working on dating sites

Dating chatbots are not a fantasy thing. They already exist and are ready to revolutionize the way we date and make new friends.

See, for example, Lara on Match.com. Lara's biggest selling point is that it gives new users a taste of what they can find on the Match.com platform.

She asks for basic details - age, location, sexual orientation, etc. - via Facebook Messenger to set up a user.

It then offers matches, which include basic profile information with a profile image.

Users can select a match, which opens the Match app to view the full profile.

Lara is more of a marketing or integration agent than a first time chat experience. It makes it easy for users to navigate before they formally set up a Match.com account.

However, once users complete a profile completely, Lara will be able to use all this data to use AI to program chatbots to chat with the user.

One of the most unique ideas for using chatbots in users has the chance to meet a person with a stolen identity photograph, according to the facial and physical choice that the user wants, through a method of successively choosing profiles with I like it - I don't like it.

The profit of the company that runs or owns the site is that each message you send to Chatbot pays an average of 1 Euro. The user has to buy messaging packages with promotions that reach 300 Euros. You can also pay to make your photo on the top more visible or be considered premium with several perks.

You can find them in sites owned by unknown companies like :

<https://www.flerteeligue.com>

<https://www.twoo.com>

<https://match.com>

<https://www.affiny.co.uk>

<https://www.benaughty.com>

<https://www.flirt.com>

<https://www.meetmilfy.com>

<https://www.erotilink.com>

<https://bumble.com>

, and many other dozens of sites each one with a national or regional section many belonging to the same company.

The user is thus completely misled because he thinks he is talking to his ideal dating and is having a conversation with a Chatbot.

Of course, Chatbot never accepts any contact other than through its platform and responds smoothly to meeting invitations that you need to know better through the conversation.

Other scheme are true call centres that hire people to chat on line paying a salary accordingly the number of messages they get from the user.

Conclusion

All this sites have a legal caution, advertising that profiles can be fiction and personal meetings are not possible. However some of the profiles are necessarily true because they are from users that are paying.

Many users get psychic diseases because they fall in love with someone they thought be human but is only a virtual chatbot.

The main question is from who are the pictures in the profiles? Stolen from the internet for sure.

We don't see in this rich industry any police or criminal investigation what makes it very strange. These are just questions and thoughts after analyzing the described phenomena that gives millions of USD \$ profits everyday.

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